
BHARAT BODH AMONG STUDENTS: EFFECTIVENESS OF EXPERIENTIAL LEARNING**Dr. Seema Bargat**Assistant Professor, Department of Education
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ABSTRACT

In the context of the National Education Policy 2020, the four-year B.A. B.Ed. ITEP program (2023–27 sessions) was initiated in the Department of Education at Mahatma Gandhi International Hindi University, Wardha (Maharashtra). According to this program, competent teachers are expected to develop. The ITEP curriculum includes the subject 'Bharat Bodh' in the first and second semesters. The teaching and learning of this subject were implemented entirely in a practical manner.

The main objective is to provide students with experiential learning rather than theoretical knowledge. So far, in two sessions, students have experienced an understanding of India through various practical activities (such as fieldwork, cultural programs, group discussions, local visits, discussions or interviews with elders, etc.)

Through this, the researcher has tried to promote experiential learning among the students.

In the present article, the researcher has analysed the experiences of students' activities. By examining the experiences of students from different states of India and diverse socio-cultural backgrounds, the study has explored the effectiveness of experiential learning activities for India Studies.

It can be concluded that experiential learning is a highly effective approach for teaching India-consciousness and, through it, Indian culture and the Indian knowledge tradition. Overall, India-consciousness has been made a medium for lively, practical, and multicultural learning, providing students with the opportunity to experience and understand the diversity and unity of India directly.

Keywords: National Education Policy 2020, Bharat Bodh, Practical, Experiential Learning, Indian Knowledge Tradition

INTRODUCTION :

'Bharat Bodh' means understanding India in its cultural, spiritual, geographical, and social form. India is an ancient, spiritual, and eternal cultural entity whose unity arises from its traditions, values, and geography. River systems, temples, pilgrimages, epics like the Ramayana and Mahabharata, saints from Adi Shankaracharya to Guru Nanak, and folk cultures act as living threads connecting India's past with its present and future. Great personalities such as the naturalist Rabindranath Tagore, the pragmatic and founder of Nai Talim, Mahatma Gandhi, the visionary Dayanand Saraswati, and the youthful consciousness Swami Vivekananda have all focused on the 'holistic development of the child.'

Indian culture, based on the philosophy of "Sarve Bhavantu Sukhinah (Bruhdarny Upnishd 1.4.14) and "Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam," Mahaupnishd guides society and truly makes 'Bharat' an 'Atulya aur Anupm Bharat'.

UNDERSTANDING BHARAT BODH:**A Cultural and Experiential Perspective**

'Bharat Bodh' means understanding and embracing one's roots, culture, religion, and knowledge traditions, rather than relying on imported ideologies. 'Bharat Bodh' signifies an awareness of the soul of India, its civilization, history, values, and cultural Heritage. If this awareness is deeply developed among students, it not only awakens a sense of patriotism in them but also helps them understand their responsibilities towards society and the nation. In this process, experiential learning proves to be the most effective method.

Explaining the concept of 'Bharat', Dr Manmohan Vaidya, co-general secretary and thinker of the Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh, says, "**Bharat ko mano, fir Bharat ko jano uske nad Bharat ke bno aur sbse akhir me Bharat ko bnavo**"

Objectives

1. To familiarise students deeply with Indian culture, tradition, history, and values through India Studies.
2. Effective education comes more from direct experiences and activities than from book knowledge.
3. To instil in students a sense of patriotism, national pride, responsibility, and pride in India's unity and diversity.
4. Develop respect and empathy towards different communities, languages, and traditions to build social and cultural sensitivity.
5. Promote students' creativity through various activities.
6. Make students realise that knowledge comes from reading, exams, and living and doing.
7. Develop a sense of social responsibility, cooperation, and inclination to work for the nation's welfare in students to make them responsible citizens.

ROLE OF EXPERIENTIAL LEARNING-

Experiential learning is based on " krke sikhna " When students understand India's history, culture, and social structure through activities, projects, and authentic experiences related to India, they do not limit the subject to the textbook alone, but internalise it. This method provides students with information and allows them to connect with that information.

The New Education Policy (NEP) 2020 has considered experiential learning as the focal point of education, which reduces the tendency to rote learning and enhances the ability to think and understand. On this basis, providing experiential learning in Bharat Bodh is relevant.

Educational trips, whether village visits or study tours, connect students with historical sites and cultural Heritage. India-exploration related project work, such as studying and surveying local history or cultural Heritage, also familiarises students with the diversity and harmony of society.

METHODOLOGY

The present B.A.B.Ed ITEP course started in session (2023–27) in the Department of Education at Mahatma Gandhi International Hindi University, Wardha (Maharashtra). In the first year, written examinations through question papers were conducted in both semesters,

after which the university's academic board decided to make the subject of Bharat Bodh entirely practical. Students were grouped according to their interest in the topic, and a framework of practical activities was designed. Activities were implemented in the order of presentations, discussions, questions, resolution of queries, and feedback. So far, 200 students have participated in the activities of this research work, and the analysis has been provided in the present article.

EXPERIENTIAL ACTIVITIES OF THE FIRST-YEAR 'BHARAT BODH' SUBJECT

Initially, the researcher introduced Indian knowledge traditions, the Gurukul education system, objectives of education, methods, educational values, Vedas, Puranas, Upanishads, religious texts, etc., in various sessions.

1. **Bharat Darshan Project** - Each student in the class was asked to select a state or region of India. They researched that region's culture, attire, cuisine, language, folk art, etc., and shared their experiences through a presentation.
1. **2 Culture** - Art and Literature Fine Arts - The study of fine arts of different states, including what forms traditional art takes, what contemporary art exists, the relationship between art and spirituality, what recognition comes from art, and how art can be globalized, was presented in a group.
2. **3 Performing Arts** - A presentation was made after studying dance systems of different states, traditional forms of music, visual arts, and folk arts.
3. **Literature** - Presentations were given after selecting, according to interest, Sanskrit literature of different states, religious literature, Bhartiya kavita, folk literature, Bhartiya katha, Kannada, Malayalam literature, Bengali literature, etc.

5. ENVIRONMENT:

Studying society's perceptions about resources like forests, land, water, and animals is essential to understanding the balance between society and the environment. Therefore, direct field observations were conducted in society. The relationship of festivals and celebrations with the environment was explored through local visits, and experiences were shared in the presentation. Additionally, historical visits were conducted to understand where sustainable architecture is located across India and the role of sustainable architecture in urban planning. Group discussions and PowerPoint presentations on solutions to today's environmental challenges were held.

6 HISTORICAL SITE VISIT -

Organise visits to local historical sites or museums to allow students to understand and experience the historical background there, followed by group presentations.

7. HEALTH TRADITIONS OF BHARAT –

Today, no matter how modern we have become, students collect information related to India's health traditions, including Ayurveda, Siddha, Ashtavaidya, Unani, and other texts like the Sushruta Samhita and Charaka Samhita, and present and discuss it. They also consulted with relevant experts on ancient India's time-tested concepts of mental health and mental well-being, including how the mind, meditation, Ayurveda, yoga philosophy, soul, etc., benefit human life.

Experiential activities for the second-year subject 'Bharat Bodh':

1. **Philosophy, Ethics, and Value** – Knowledge Inquiry: Understanding the relevance of Vedanta in today's times and learning to apply ethics in a technologically unstable world.
2. **Spirituality and Social Responsibility:** Recognising the importance of spirituality in the present time and prioritising living a moral and contemporary life.
3. **Culture - Lifestyle -**
 - a. **Food** - Regional dishes, Ayurveda diet, food and festivals, vegetarianism, Jain food practices, food and hospitality, learning about how food has transitioned from traditional to globalize.
 - b. **Clothing** - Traditional Indian clothing, textiles and art, religious attire, status associated with clothing, clothing and gender, becoming familiar with the reality of globalisation in apparel.
 - c. **Sports** - Rediscovering forgotten traditional Indian games, martial arts, sports and gender, developing curiosity about sports and globalization.
 - d. **Yoga** - Yoga as a lifestyle, one can progress towards longevity by adopting ancient ways of life; this can be learned through daily yoga and prayer practices.

4. Science and Technology –

We became familiar with India's contribution to astronomy across the world. We learned about the Indian concepts of time and space since ancient times, and visited a religious site in Wardha to understand how time was measured.

5. Linguistic Traditions –

A visit was made to the university's Department of Literature and Linguistics to clarify the concepts of the history of linguistics in India, ancient Indian linguistics, oral traditions, etc., to understand language, culture, and history. After the presentation, discussions are held, and practical activities that enable student teachers are conducted. In this, students took the help of family members, elders, neighbours, and other members of society.

Summary of the lessons learned from each state through the activities of the 'Bharat Darshan Scheme' -

Students selected different states of India according to their interest and gave presentations. This not only developed their research abilities and presentation skills but also provided an opportunity to experience the diversity of India. Each state offered some unique lessons, which are presented below point-wise.

State-Specific Learning

Maharashtra -The land of saints and great personalities, the history of the Marathas, Warli paintings, the Ganpati festival, and the inspiration for social reform movements

Rajasthan -A land of heroes and heroines, filled with architectural art, desert culture, folk music, and a diversity of colours.

Madhya pradesh -It is a state located in the heart of India, filled with historical monuments, rich cultural Heritage, diverse wildlife, and natural beauty.

Sikkim-They attract tourists with their peaceful environment and multicultural traditions, practice organic farming, and never start any movements.

Bangal-Rabindranath Tagore's legacy, Durga Puja, intellectuality, and art-culture

Nagaland-Traditional handloom, tribal lifestyle, and harmony with nature

odisa -Ancient temples, vibrant culture, and unique tribes coexist with modern progress.

Impact of Experiential Learning from the Perspective of 'Bharat Bodh': Experiential learning has shown several positive effects on students –

1. A deep sensitivity and internalization were manifested among the students –

After the presentation, instead of merely memorizing facts, the students began to experience the diversity of India. For example, learning about a state's folk art, discussing its cuisine, or visiting a historical site provided an opportunity to feel a sense of 'Bharat Bodh'.

2. There has been an improvement in communication and expression skills –

While sharing experiences, students began to express their ideas more effectively during presentations. Sharing experiences has enhanced communication skills and confidence. The reflective activities conducted directly encouraged them to think critically and self-analysis. Understanding the diversity of India has developed analytical thinking and a multi-perspective approach..

3. Creativity and fostering socio-cultural connections with India's roots and values –

After the introduction to various states of India, engagement with traditional arts, languages, and customs encouraged creativity among students. Cultural activities enhanced students' imagination and creativity. They learned to see India's diversity as a unifying thread and began to respect each other's cultures.

4. Problem-solving and leadership skills were developed –

After the group presentation, experiential learning helped students develop teamwork, a sense of collaboration, leadership, and decision-making abilities. This reduced mutual differences. Development of Patriotism and a Sense of Unity

5. A sense of patriotism and unity has developed –

We became familiar with the concepts of patriotism and nationalism, and the introduction to various states fostered a sense of unity. Awareness of duty and social responsibility also increased.

CONCLUSION:

Describing activities in the presented topic provides an effective approach towards making education practical, interactive, and culturally enriched. Experiential activities provide students with knowledge and allow them to "live" and "understand" the true essence of India. Developing a sense of India in students is impossible through bookish knowledge alone. Experiential learning allows them to experience India's culture, traditions, and values.

Conveying 'Bharat Bodh' to students through experiential learning is not merely an educational experiment, but a nation-building process. It takes them from information to experience, knowledge to awareness, and education to values.

KEY FINDINGS:

1. Emotional attachment to India was developed –

Experiential activities such as exploring India's various states' folk art, culture, and regional cuisine strengthened students' pride and affinity towards the country.

2. **Development of a comprehensive and in-depth understanding** -Students viewed India as a geographical entity and a vibrant cultural experience. This enhanced their critical thinking, cultural tolerance, and inclusivity.

3. **Improvement in creativity and expression skills** –

Experiential learning provided students a platform to express their creativity through India's diversity, such as through dance, painting, theatrical performances, writing, etc.

4. **Development of communication and collaboration skills** –

Group activities and presentations enhanced students' sense of teamwork, leadership, and cooperation throughout the session.

5. **Developed a sense of national unity and social responsibility** –

Understanding the diversity of India strengthened the concept of unity in diversity among students. Students became more sensitive and aware of social issues..

It can be concluded from this that 'Bharat Bodh' and the experiential learning of it are an efficient approach for teaching Indian culture and the Indian knowledge tradition. In other words, experiential learning enables teachers and students to study Bharat Bodh in depth.

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